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A Creative Folio

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Wisdom Home: Edifying Minds, Shaping Hearts, Changing Lives

The sun was starting to flash its bright smile, slowly lighting up as the world began to awake. I woke up and started doing some stretching as I heard the trees swaying in the wind. I ate my heavy breakfast and then began to walk to school.

As I walked around the school, I greeted every staff member and teacher I saw. Eventually, I reached the classroom and then put down my ponderous bag on my old chocolate-brown chair. The atmosphere was quiet and peaceful; it was only 6:30 in the morning, which was the primary reason why we were only three students present in the classroom. Soon, many students began entering the classroom, which made the ambiance more lively and bubbly. As more students entered the schoolroom, it started to be obnoxiously blasting. However, as soon as we heard a familiar footstep, in just a glimpse, all the standing and running around of the students turned to sitting down. The students who were yelling taped their mouths shut; it was all because our teacher had entered the room.

We all grabbed our books and began flipping through the pages that our teacher asked us to read. He was not a terror teacher, yet you would not want to get on his terrible side. One time, when we were not paying attention to the lesson, he stopped discussing. Then told us to get one whole sheet of paper. "Number your papers, from 1-100," he spoke in such an unruffled mode that it gave the chills to our spine. The teacher, who we thought was nice enough to joke around with us, suddenly became one of the teachers we were frightened of. None of us was able to answer that test. Afterward, he asked us why we could not answer the test. He gathered our papers and then spoke, "If you actually paid attention to the discussion instead of chattering with your seatmate, you would have passed this test."

We all sighed in assurance when he did not record the test, for we all apologized right after. The section known to be the wildest of all was finally tamed. Right after that, ironically, the wildest section was known to be the most disciplined section. Despite all that, we loved our teacher. Though he was strict, we actually learned things beyond academics because of him. Our whole perspective of the academy changed. We all once thought that school was just a place to study different academic tracks, but we were mistaken. It was not just a place to study; it was a place where we learn a variety of crucial and decisive things that will be subservient to our future.

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School is not only there to teach us to count in Mathematics, to explore Sciences, and to speak up our minds in English and other curricular activities; it is there to make us enjoy discovering diversity, help us develop our talents, follow our dreams and visions, and most importantly, school teaches us to be well-mannered and refined human beings.

School is more than a home; it is where we are all nurtured to be individuals who will someday be a catalyst for change in this failing society; it is where our minds were enlightened and edified, where our hearts were being shaped, and where our lives were changed to be a testimony and inspiration to everyone. A class home where our talents, knowledge, and wisdom were cultivated for us to be good citizens of our country.